

Impact of reference value selection on one-sample comparisons of quality of life in AML survivors

Dennis Görlich¹, Cristina Sauerland¹, Eva Telzerow²
Anna S Moret², Simon M Krauß³, Klaus H Metzeler³

¹Institute of Biostatistics and Clinical Research, University Münster, Münster, Germany

²Department of Medicine III and Comprehensive Cancer Center, University Hospital, LMU Munich, Munich, Germany

³Department of Hematology, Cell Therapy and Hemostaseology, University of Leipzig, Leipzig, Germany

Abstract

Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML) survivors often experience long-term effects on their quality of life (QoL). When evaluating QoL outcomes, one-sample comparison tests may sometimes be the only option to determine whether mean scores differ significantly from a (healthy) comparator group. However, the choice of these reference values can substantially influence results and interpretations. This study investigates how different reference value selection methods affect one-sample comparisons of QoL in AML survivors. The theoretical approaches are illustrated using data from a cohort of AML long term survivors. We examined the impact of three methods to construct reference values on test statistics, p-values, and the conclusions drawn about QoL differences. Our findings highlight the importance of careful consideration of confounders when selecting reference values for one-sample tests. The implications of our research are discussed in terms of improving the accuracy and reliability of QoL assessments in cancer survivorship studies.

Key Words: One-sample testing, quality of life, reference value definition

1. Background & Motivation

Between 2017 and 2020, 427 former patients treated for an Acute Myeloid Leukemia (AML) were invited and agreed to participate in a cross-sectional assessment of quality of life (QoL) and life satisfaction (LS) during the long-term survivor phase. The study protocol did not foresee a direct parallel comparator group, nor were other comparator individual participant data (IPD) for the selected outcome measures available. Thus, the only statistical option to draw inference on QoL and LS in long-term survivors was given by one-sample comparisons to theoretical mean values, or better phrased in the context of this analysis, reference values. The study protocol formulated a z-standardization against published reference values derived from a non-AML population. The present article aims to give a concise evaluation of different methods to justify reference values for one-sample comparisons. A special focus will be put on incorporation of confounders of reference values, which, if not respected, threaten representativeness and ultimately may lead to wrong results. This article describes three methodological approaches to use reference values in one-sample tests (Section 2), present results applying a data example from the motivating AML LTS dataset (Section 3) and lastly gives conclusions and an outlook (Section 4).

2. Methods to address reference values for one-sample comparisons

2.1 General considerations

For all following methods, we consider typical one-sample tests using the following notation. Given is a dataset of N independent and identically distributed observations of a continuous outcome Y_i , with $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$. Additionally, p covariates of each observation are known and denoted as Z_{ij} with $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ and $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, p\}$. Z_{ij} may be either continuous or categorical covariates.

Furthermore, a theoretical value θ_0 is given as a reference value. Typically, a null hypothesis of the form $H_0: \mathbb{E}(Y_i) = \theta_0$ will be tested to draw inference over the shift of the underlying distribution compared to the theoretical value. Of course, other null hypotheses might be of interest (e.g. quantiles), but will not be discussed within this article. Of note, the presented methods will not depend on the chosen statistical test for the specific one-sample null hypothesis. A major prerequisite for meaningful inferences in this setting is, that values of θ_0 are representative for the selected comparison group. Mis-specified reference values can lead to wrong inferences and thus threaten the interpretability of results.

2.2 Source of missing representativeness of reference values

We usually call a sample (the research data) representative, if its distribution of relevant socio-demographic or clinical parameters is aligned to a target population [1]. The Cochrane handbook defines selection bias as the result of “systematic differences between baseline characteristics of the groups that are compared.”[2]. Bias, as systematic error, can lead to under- or over-estimation of effects or other impacts often hard to detect and prevent [3]. If a direct comparator group is available, a number of methodological approaches are available to regain sufficient representativeness to draw valid conclusions from a statistical analysis. Among these methods are randomization [3], matching (e.g. direct matching, or propensity scores) [4], or multivariable regression models [5]. While bias is mainly characterized by a difference in the distribution, some confounders might be more influential than others. Such major confounders are covariates, which are associated with the outcome variable that is used to compute the reference value. Association usually is detected statistically by correlation (either directly, or as part of a regression model). Other more complex forms of associations might also prevail. For our article, the simple form of association will be sufficient to motivate the presented methods. We can assess the difference $D(P||Q)$ between the distribution of cofactor $P = Z_j^C$ in the comparator and in the experimental group ($Q = Z_j^E$) e.g. using Kullback-Leibler $KL(P, Q)$ divergence. A relevant cofactor j is characterized by a correlation $\rho_{Z_j, X} > \rho_{crit}$ larger than a defined critical value. Taken together, two situations can occur:

$$|D(Z_j^C || Z_j^E)| < d_{crit} \quad \text{OR} \quad |\rho_{Z_j, Y}| < \rho_{crit} : \text{confounder distribution is comparable and confounder influence on outcome X is negligible.}$$

$$|D(Z_j^C || Z_j^E)| > d_{crit} \quad \text{AND} \quad |\rho_{Z_j, Y}| > \rho_{crit} : \text{confounder distribution is not comparable and confounder influence on outcome X is relevant.}$$

The second case signifies a situation where reference values drawn from the comparison group are not representative for any inference made with the experimental group. We here will illustrate this situation using an example utilized also in section 5 of this article. Briefly, we analyzed FACT-G scores as quality of life outcome in AML survivors. Reference values from a non-AML cohort were only available in form of aggregated means and standard deviations. Also, the age distribution of the comparator data was known as well as the effect of age on the outcome. Furthermore, we know that the age distribution of AML patients (and thus survivors) will be different. Table 1 shows the two age distributions. The KL divergence is 0.54, which has to be considered large in this example. This also corresponds to the chi-squared test result of the AML LTS data against the theoretical age distribution of the comparator data.

Table 1: Kullback-Leibler divergence of age distributions. $KL(\text{Comparator}||\text{AML LTS})=0.54$.
Chi-square test (AML LTS data vs theoretical distribution of Comparator): $p < 0.0001$.

Cohort	18-29y	30-39y	40-49y	50-59y	60-69y	70y+
Comparator	11.4%	22.7%	19.4%	17.9%	14.7%	13.8%
AML LTS	1.4%	7.3%	9.6%	28.1%	30.2%	23.4%

To further justify that large KL divergence found in our example we performed a simulation study and systematically compared chi-squared test results with KL divergence. The simulation study draws random age values from a normal distribution and reports chi-squared test and KL divergence. Figure 1B shows that KL divergence is lowest when the distribution is near the average age of the reference (here 48 years). Figure 1A shows that KL divergence and X^2 test statistics have a clear relationship. A linear model estimates that the KL-cut-off value is at 0.078 (i.e. the KL divergence

where on average the critical X^2 value for $df=5$ test with $\alpha=0.05$ will be met). For divergence larger than the cut-off the X^2 usually also rejects the null hypothesis of identical distributions (in our data example). For each reference cohort and cofactor, this value will differ. This example shows how d_{crit} can be motivated. This kind of diagnostic analysis helps to identify problems when comparing data with a reference cohort. Of course, such an analysis is only feasible when the comparator groups is sufficiently well sized and characterized in the presentation of aggregated results.

Figure 1. A) Scatter plot of a simulation study comparing Kullback-Leiber divergence (KL) between age distributions and the corresponding X^2 test statistic. Random age distributions with $\text{Age} \sim \text{Normal}(\text{age}, 20)$ were drawn and compared to the theoretical age distribution observed in Holzner (2004). B) Relationship between KL and age in the simulation study.

2.3 Methods to regain representativeness

All of the following methods can be applied in situations where confounder distributions mismatch and the confounder is well correlated with the outcome. For this article, we will only describe the case that one major confounder is adjusted for. Also, all methods can be generalized to a multivariate situation.

2.3.1 Reweighting

The reweighting approach is applicable for null hypotheses of the form $H_0: \mathbb{E}(Y) = \theta_0$. Observed outcome values are tested against the theoretical value of the comparator group. In the presence of confounding bias, as described in the previous section, the reference value θ_0 may be representative for the comparator, but not a good reference value for the observed cohort. In case of a categorical confounder, e.g. age groups, we propose to reweight θ_0 , i.e. compute a new θ_0^* using the available aggregated reference data in combination with the observed distribution of the confounder. Formally, a reference value θ_0 that is derived from a comparator group can be computed $\theta_0 = \sum w_k \cdot E(Y|k)$, i.e. θ_0 can be considered the mean of the conditional expectations within each category of the confounder weighted by the probability that this category is present, i.e. the relative frequency. Reweighting is introduced by exchanging the weights w_k by the observed weights w_k^* from the experimental group. Thus, $\theta_0^* = \sum w_k^* \cdot E(Y|k)$. By this, the distributional mismatch (KL divergence) is handled and the newly computed reference value θ_0^* is shifted to be more representative. This does not mean that test results will be made more similar. The reweighting only results in a more fair/less biased comparison, between the comparator (e.g. an untreated group or non-disease comparator) and the experimental group. A multivariate extension is easily implemented by using reference values $E(Y|k, l, \dots)$ stratified for more confounders and, respectively, using weights for each stratum that emerges from the combination of confounders.

2.3.2 External z-standardization

The usage of external z-standardization is applicable for the following type of null hypotheses $H_0: E(z) = 0$, where z is a transformation of Y such that an external (i.e. from the comparator) mean μ and standard deviation σ are used for standardization: $z(Y) = \frac{Y-\mu}{\sigma}$. The choice of the external information for standardization determines the results of the statistical test. In the presence of

confounding, as described before, we strongly suggest using conditional means and standard deviations. I.e. for each stratum of the relevant confounder Z a different μ and σ needs to be available from the comparator cohort. Then, a stratified z-value can be computed $z_i^* = \frac{Y_i - \mu_{k(i)}}{\sigma_{k(i)}}$ for each subject from the experimental group, with $\mu_{k(i)}$ as reference values from the stratum that represents the value of the confounder observed for X_i . A similarly approach should be chosen for $\sigma_{k(i)}$. Thus each subject will be compared, in form of a z-value, with the mean of his or her peer group, having the same confounder value. E.g. older females will be compared with the outcome of their respective peer group in the comparator. This means all subjects from the same stratum will be compared to the same stratum-specific reference value. If, under the null-hypothesis, the distribution of outcomes is similar to the comparator in each stratum, then z should be on average zero and the global null hypothesis as shown above can be applied. A multivariate extension can easily be implemented by using strata defined by the combination of confounders.

2.3.3 Individual model-based reference values

Finally, we here propose a model-based approach for reference value determination. Since we know that in the relevant scenarios (i) a distributional mismatch exists and (ii) a relevant correlation between confounder and outcome exists, we can use this relationship between both to establish a prediction model. This model then can be used to predict the expected reference value for the experimental group for each subject individually. Optimally, such a prediction model would be published directly with the reference values, e.g. in form a (potentially) linear regression model. Formally, we aim to test the null hypothesis $H_0: (E(Y) - E(R)) = 0$. Given a prediction model for a typical (i.e. reference) value base on covariates Z , defined by a function $g(\cdot)$, for each subject a difference can be computed $\Delta_i = Y_i - g(Z_i)$. The null hypothesis reduces to $H_0: E(\Delta) = 0$. The function $g(\cdot)$ is estimated from the reference data and is only dependent on the joint support of confounders.

3. Application to the AML Survivorship trial

3.1 The AML Survivorship study

Between 2017 and 2020, the AML Survivorship study (AML LTS, DRKS00023991)[6,7] recruited 427 former patients who were treated for their acute myeloid leukemia (AML) in the AMLCG study group (www.aml-germany.com). Participants of the AML LTS study were adult long-term survivors (LTS) of at least 5 years with no current relapse. The primary aim was to describe psychosocial and somatic status of survivors of AML. Quality of life (QoL) and life satisfaction (LS), were assessed by the FACT-G questionnaire and the FLZ^m questionnaires as patient-reported outcome measures (PROM). For comparison with an expected normal reference value, the z-standardization was applied as described in section 2.3.2. This methodology was fixed in a study protocol before recruitment started. Telzerow et al. (currently under review) reported the primary results of the study. The FACT-G questionnaire was initially published by [8] and aims at the quality of life of cancer survivors. We selected this measure for good reliability (test-retest correlation 0.92 for the total score, [8]; Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.7$ for all subscales, [9]) and comparability with other trials. The available reference values were taken from Holzner et al. (2004) [9]. Therein, mean FACT-G scores were published by sex and age subgroups, allowing to adjust for both important co-variables. The reference data show a clear trend with age, but only marginal differences between males and females. The overall mean FACT-G reference values was $\theta_{ref} = 86$.

Figure 2. Mean FACT-G values by sex and age subgroups. Adapted from Holzner (2004).

3.2 Results of the reweighting approach

Our simulation study using a null-model (i.e. random values are drawn from the reference value population) illustrates the impact of covariate based reweighting of the reference value on the proportion of rejections (Figure 2A). In each simulation replication, 427 random FACT-G values were drawn based on a random patient age, which itself was drawn from a normal distribution. The x-axes of Figures 2A and B show the selected mean of this normal age distribution. As the green lines (testing based on Holzner reference values w/o reweighting) indicates, the proportion of rejection increases quickly, when the covariate distribution (here age) moves away from the observed covariate distribution of the reference cohort. The reference cohort had an age mean of 48 years. As the blue line shows, the proportion of rejections under the null model is around 5% (the selected alpha of the one-sample test) when the reweighting approach for θ_0 (Section 2.3.1) is applied. Figure 2B shows that the correction works independently from a potential effect, i.e. when the alternative hypothesis is true.

Figure 2. Results of the simulation study. A) Under the null-model the proportion of rejections should be around 5% (given a two-sided one-sample statistical test with $\alpha=5\%$). Green: Simulation of shifted age distributions w/o reweighting. Blue: Simulation of shifted age distributions with reweighting of the reference value. B) Simulation results of the corrected test under assumption of an effect.

3.3 Results of the external z-standardization approach

We used the published reference values in three different manners,

- (i) by using the overall mean $\theta_{ref} = 86$ uniformly for all survivors, i.e. $z_i^{total} = \frac{x_i - \mu_{total}}{\sigma_{total}}$
- (ii) by using an age-group specific standardization, i.e. $z_i^{age} = \frac{x_i - \mu_{age(i)}}{\sigma_{age(i)}}$, with $age(i)$ indicating to select reference mean and standard deviation from the age stratum where survivor i is situated.
- (iii) By using and age- and sex-stratum specific standardization, i.e. $z_i^{age,sex} = \frac{x_i - \mu_{age(i),sex(i)}}{\sigma_{age(i),sex(i)}}$. Figure 3 shows the result of this transformation.

Correlation between the three different ways to reach a standardization using stratified reference values were very high ($r > 0.97$, for all pairs) and the distributional form of the three z-scores was very similarly skewed (Table 2). The application of non-parametric test for location shows different behaviours of the three variants (Table 2). We tested the two-sided null-hypothesis $H_0: z = 0$ using non-parametric tests. If survivor data is distributed like reference data we expect a zero difference. The analysis shows that using the overall average and standard deviation leads to a different result, than using age or age and sex in the standardization. Furthermore, using age alone seems to be sufficient to reach a significant test result. Adding sex into the standardization changes the testing result only marginally.

Figure 3. Standardization of observed total FACT-G scores (x-axis) into age- and sex- standardized z-values.

Table 2: Results of non-parametric two-sided testing $H_0: z = 0$ after applying three different methods of z-standardization.

Standardization method	Mean z (SD)	Median z (MAD)	Skewness	Test statistic	p-value
z_i^{total}	-0.036 (1.0)	0.16 (1.39)	-1.03	2406	.3343
z_i^{age}	0.105 (0.96)	0.31 (1.34)	-1.04	9210	.0001
$z_i^{age,sex}$	0.106 (0.98)	0.30 (1.35)	-1.07	9869	<.0001

SD – standard deviation; MAD – median average deviation.

The z-standardization also allows to analyze effects in age-subgroups. The overall significant shift in age and age-sex standardized z-values seems to be mainly introduced into the data by the older age groups (Figure 4). Although, younger survivors also show increased FACT-G scores the sample size within the younger age-subgroups lead to decreased power. Thus, we could not prove this increased QoL (compared to the reference cohort) statistically. The naïve approach to use the overall mean (z^{total}) for standardization leads to a trend of decreasing z-scores over age groups. This trend mimics the overall trend in the reference data (Figure 2). Especially, in the age-stratum 50-59, which is near the reference age mean (48 years) the z-score reaches a median of 0.

Figure 4. Median, skewness and p-values of age-subgroups. P-values correspond to two-sided one-sample non-parametric tests of z-values after standardization with the reference values (published in [9]). P-value y-axis is scaled in log10 units.

Table 3: A-posteriori power calculation to detect selected potential effect sizes (Cohens' d) with a two-sided non-parametric one-sample test in the age-subgroups, using the observed sample size.

Age (years)	<29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	70+
N	6	31	41	120	129	100
Power (d=0.15)	6%	12%	15%	36%	38%	31%
Power (d=0.2)	7%	18%	23%	56%	60%	49%
Power (d=0.5)	16%	74%	86%	99%	99%	99%

3.4 Results of the model-based approach

The model-based approach allows to compute (predict) individual expected values for a survivor based on his or her baseline characteristics, with respect to the selected relevant strata. The reference values were reported in age groups. Since age is a continuous variable, we will use age as continuous factor in a linear regression model. The linear regression model was estimated using the published means within the age-sex strata. Optimally, the model would have been estimated from the raw data, but those are not available for this analysis. In case a regression model was published with the original reference data, this should be used. For our analysis three models could be estimated depending on the positioning of reference values on the lower, upper or midpoint of the age-group range. Table 4 shows the sex-specific regression models using age as continuous factor. As described above we test the null-hypothesis $H_0: (E(Y) - E(R))$. Figure 5A shows the shift of regression models based on anchor point (red: lower; blue: midpoint; green: upper bound), while in Fig. 5B the effect on test statistics can be seen. The negative trend in the relation between FACT-G and age leads to a shift in test statistics.

Table 4: Regression models by sex for expected FACT-G values based on published reference values.

		Low	Mid point	Upper
Women	β_0	96.1	97.45	98.18
	β_{age}	-0.2535	0.2563	-0.2603
	adjusted R ²	0.9171	0.926	0.9626
Men	β_0	93.7	94.4	94.7
	β_{age}	-0.1423	-0.1433	-0.1418
	adjusted R ²	0.8529	0.8514	0.8295

Figure 5. A) Linear regression models re-estimated from reference values based on lower, midpoint or upper age-subgroup values; B) Test results of one-sample Wilcoxon tests.

4. Discussion

Within this work we presented three approaches to test continuous outcomes of single cohorts, i.e. in a one-sample setting, against reference values, e.g. from a non-cancer population. Our approach can be applied when no individual patient data is available for two-sample comparisons. Here, we discussed the impact of age and sex as major confounders in QoL. In other applications different confounders may play a role. We used Kullback-Leibler distances as a statistical measures for bias, in terms of distances of covariate distributions. A threshold value can be motivated from this but is part of further research. Our approach can be flexibly used for one or more confounding variables, either categorical or continuous, as long as reliable reference data is available. Our application onto the AML survivorship study illustrates that these approaches are necessary and data analysis can be impacted significantly. Thus, a pre-specification, as realized in the AML survivorship study protocol, is necessary to allow for transparent and unbiased data analysis.

Acknowledgements

We like to thank all former patients who participated in the AMLCG trials and agreed to participate in our survivorship study. We also acknowledge the ongoing support of the AMLCG study group especially Prof. Wolfgang Hiddemann, Prof. Karsten Spiekermann, Prof. Wolfgang Berdel, Prof. Bernhard Wörmann, Prof. Utz Krug and Prof. Jan Braess for their leadership and expert knowledge in the field. We also thank Elke Burgard and Oleg Choubine, from the Institute of Biostatistics and Clinical Research of the University of Münster, for their support during study conduct. The study was supported by funding of the German Jose Carreras Leukemia Foundation (DJCLS, 13R/2019).

References

1. Rudolph, Jacqueline E et al. Defining representativeness of study samples in medical and population health research. *BMJ Medicine* vol. 2,1 e000399. 2023.
2. Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA (editors). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions* version 6.5 (updated August 2024). Cochrane, 2024. Available from www.training.cochrane.org/handbook.
3. Odgaard-Jensen J, Vist GE, Timmer A, et al. Randomisation to protect against selection bias in healthcare trials. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2011;2011(4):MR000012.
4. Stuart, Elizabeth A. "Matching methods for causal inference: A review and a look forward." *Statistical science : a review journal of the Institute of Mathematical Statistics* vol. 25,1 (2010): 1-21. doi:10.1214/09-STS313

5. McNamee R. Regression modelling and other methods to control confounding. *Occup Environ Med* 2005;62:500–6.
6. Study registration: Quality of life and late effects in leukemia survivors (AML SURVIVORSHIP). URL: <https://drks.de/search/de/trial/DRKS00023991>
7. Telzerow E, Görlich D, Sauerland MC et al. Life Satisfaction and Quality of Life in AML Long-Term Survivors: Primary Results of the AMLCG-Survivorship Study. *Blood* 2022; 140 (Supplement 1): 5293–5295.
8. Cella DF, Tulsky DS, Gray G, et al. The Functional Assessment of Cancer Therapy scale: development and validation of the general measure. *J Clin Oncol.* 1993;11(3):570-579.
9. Holzner B, Kemmler G, Cella D, et al. Normative data for functional assessment of cancer therapy--general scale and its use for the interpretation of quality of life scores in cancer survivors. *Acta Oncol.* 2004;43(2):153-160.